

Qualitative research on the economic innovation potential of coastal vegetated ecosystems in Germany

Research and study report are part of the project “Searching for solutions for Carbon-sequestration in coastal ecosystems (sea4soCiety): Innovative Approaches to Enhancing the Carbon Storage Potential of Coastal Vegetated Ecosystems”

1. Background and context

The project “Searching for solutions for Carbon-sequestration in coastal ecosystems (sea4soCiety)”, is part of the Deutsche Allianz Meeresforschung research mission CDRmare, financed by the Federal German Ministry for Research and Education. The social science part of the project is based at the University of Hamburg, in the working group of Prof. Dr. Beate Ratter. The project has study sites in Germany, Malaysia, Indonesia, and Columbia. Within Germany both coasts (Northern Sea and Baltic Sea) are studied by natural and social scientists.

1.1 Content and structure of the project

The project sea4soCiety aims to understand the potential of coastal vegetated ecosystems (CVEs) to sequester and store carbon dioxide through their natural processes. CVEs studied in the project include seagrass beds, saltmarshes, mangroves, and seaweed. With accelerating climate change the need for so called negative emissions becomes more relevant and the project tries to close some research gaps on the formerly often neglected CVEs. The work done within sea4soCiety ranges from quantifying carbon fluxes and storages, to mapping of the ecosystems to laboratory work on their hydrological properties. However, sea4soCiety also investigates the socio-economic dimension of the use, conservation, and expansion of the CVEs, for the coasts and their ecosystems are highly connected to the local communities and people. The project is embedded in the research mission “Marine carbon sinks in decarbonization pathways”, which explores different ways on how the oceans can help to achieve net-zero emissions.

For the German coasts the economic innovation potential of coastal vegetated ecosystems, as well as the people’s perception on them was researched. For the work on perception, see the related work of M. Fink. The here described data set and report is on the economic innovation potential. So far CVEs in Germany are rarely used and if so, mainly in terms of their raw material, e.g., saltmarshes for grazing, seagrass washed and dried for insulation or cushioning. Therefore, the aim of the study was to find out if there is an innovation potential for the economic utilization of the CVEs. This ranges from new products made from seagrass and seaweed to carbon credits from blue carbon projects within the saltmarshes (or seagrass meadows), to the possibility of the establishment of complete value chains within a circular economy thinking. Focus hereby lies on the regional economy and its development with a geographical focus on Schleswig-Holstein and Lower Saxony, due to the project’s alignment. Our overarching research questions were

- 1) What is the economic innovation potential of CVEs in Germany?
- 2) What fosters and hinders developments in the economic use of CVEs?

1.2 Research methodology

For our data acquisition we used a qualitative social science approach with explorative and expert interviews as well as workshops. With the aim of the study being to identify the innovation potential, the focus was on the actors’ experiences and perspectives. Therefore, we first conducted the

interviews to get a deeper understanding on the situation so far and afterwards the workshops, to discuss possible futures and to give the actors room to exchange with each other.

2. Data generation: Preparation and implementation

The data we collected to answer our research questions is divided into five different parts. The explorative interviews, expert interviews with climate change mitigation managers, expert interviews with entrepreneurs, a two-day future search workshop and a one-day solution finding workshop. The interviewees and the workshop participants were beforehand informed on the purpose of the data acquisition and how the data would be used and stored. All were informed, that they could end the interview or leave the workshop whenever they would like, with no negative effects. Recording of the interviews and workshops was done openly with verbal approval of the participants in advance. For all data can be traced back to an individual, which could lead to negative consequences, anonymity was guaranteed.

2.1 Selection of interview partners and workshop participants

- **Explorative interview** partners first through personal contacts by Prof. Dr. B. Ratter, and project partners, then by advice of first interviewees, 5 in total (2 wadden sea National Parks: Schleswig-Holstein & Lower Saxony, 1 nature conservation agency, 1 economic development agency, 1 technological transfer center)
- **Expert interviews with climate mitigation managers** of the counties in Schleswig-Holstein: requested of all coastal counties (9), confirmation for an interview 3 (one Northern Sea, two Baltic Sea, with one from an urban county and one from a rural one)
- **Expert interviews with entrepreneurs:** interview partners selected by the advice of the explorative interview partners in combination with an extensive internet search, in total 5 interviews
- Workshop participants for the **Future Search Workshop:** former interview partners, identified actors from regional politics, nature conservation and further entrepreneurs who were not interviewed beforehand, day one invited 29, participated 9; day two invited 18, participated 4
- Workshop participants for the **Solution Finding Workshop:** through further interviews, meetings and an internet search identified actors working with the topic, invited 34, participated 6

2.2 Methods, instruments and process of data generation

- **Explorative interviews:** October 2021 – January 2022, together with colleague, in person (2) and via Zoom (3), memory protocol
- **Expert interviews with climate mitigation managers:** May 2022, via Zoom, recorded
- **Expert interviews with entrepreneurs:** May and June 2022 (2 each), January 2024 (1), in person at the company location, recorded; Guideline for the interviews was prepared structured along Porters' Diamond Model and Cookes' Regional Innovation System Approach
- **Future Search Workshop:** 04.05.2023 (day 1) and 27.11.2023 (day 2), in person in Rendsburg, Schleswig-Holstein, day 1 protocolled (written and photographed) by student assistants, day 2 recorded, graphic results on posters; The workshop agenda was prepared following the Future Search Workshop method with three consecutive phases 1) the critique phase, 2) the visionary phase and 3) the implementation phase. Phase 1 and 2 were carried out on the first workshop day and phase 3 on the second day.

- **Solution Finding Workshop:** 26.10.2023, in person in Hamburg, protocolled (written) by student assistants, graphic results on posters; The workshop agenda was adapted from the Solution Finding Workshop method

3. Cleaning of data, analysis, and future potential of data use

3.1 Data and data processing

- **Explorative interviews:** memory protocols were compared and discussed between me and my colleague
- **Expert interviews with climate mitigation managers:** recorded data was transcribed
- **Expert interviews with entrepreneurs:** recorded data was transcribed
- **Future Search Workshop:** day 1: protocols were discussed and cleaned together with the student assistants and participating colleague, day 2: recorded data was transcribed; graphic results were digitalized
- **Solution Finding Workshop:** protocols were discussed and cleaned together with the student assistants and participating colleague, graphic results were digitalized

3.2 Data analysis and results

Analysis: A content analysis of the transcripts and protocols was done along the research questions. For the workshops the preliminary results were sent to the participants for commenting. Their remarks and comments were then included to the analysis.

Results: All analyzed data flows into the internal project report on “The economic innovation potential of CVEs in Germany” (working title, language: English). The summarized results and analyzed data of the Future Search Workshops was made available for the participants (internal, language: German). The results from the Solution Finding Workshop are made into a guideline or manual (external, language: German). Scientific papers are planned which will use different combinations of the analyzed data (external, language: English).

4. Context material

For further insights on what was asked in the interviews and discussed during the workshops, the **guidelines from the expert interviews** and the **workshop agendas** are added to this data report.